

Preparation and Characterisation of Chromium(III) Complexes of Maleanilic and Phthalanilic Acids

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The complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{A-A})_3]$, where A-A = maleanilic and phthalanilic acids, and their 4-methyl, 4-chloro, 4-nitro and 1-naphthyl derivatives have been prepared. The magnetic, conductance, ir and electronic spectral studies indicate their octahedral structure.

ANILIC acids are very useful from analytical¹⁻³ and biochemical point of view⁴⁻⁶. Their complexes with calcium, aluminium and thorium ions have also been found of great industrial and biochemical importance^{7,8}, chromium(III) compounds in general occurring in brewers, yeast and other foods were found to be of outstanding biological activity. Keeping these facts in view, we are reporting in this communication the preparations and characterisation of chromium(III) complexes of maleanilic acid and its 4-methyl, 4-chloro, 4-nitro and 1-naphthyl derivatives and phthalanilic acid and its 4-methyl, 4-chloro, 4-nitro and 1-naphthyl derivatives. These complexes are also expected to be of biochemical and analytical importance.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Maleanilic acid (m.p. 205°) was prepared⁹ by treating the solution of maleic anhydride, and aniline in solvent ether at 15-20°. 4-Methyl (m.p. 201°), 4-chloro (m.p. 198°), 4-nitro (m.p. 194°) and 1-naphthyl (m.p. 200°) maleanilic acids were similarly prepared by taking the different substituted primary aromatic amines in place of aniline. Phthalanilic acid (m.p. 107°) was prepared by treating the solution of phthalic anhydride with

aniline in benzene at room temperature¹⁰, 4-methyl (m.p. 201°), 4-chloro (m.p. 199°), 4-nitro (m.p. 197°) and 1-naphthyl (m.p. 186°) phthalanilic acids were also similarly obtained by using different substituted primary aromatic amines. All these compounds were recrystallised from alcohol.

The techniques, apparatus and method of calculations were the same as reported earlier¹¹.

Preparation of complexes: Chromium hydroxide, freshly prepared by the addition of potassium hydroxide in the solution of chromium chloride, was mixed with anilic acids in the ratio of 1:4. Alcohol was then added to bring the mixture in suspended form which was refluxed on water-bath for ~6 h. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed several times with alcohol and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous sulphuric acid.

The results of chemical analysis, conductances in methanol and the values of magnetic moment at room temperature are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectral studies: The main characteristic features of the ir spectra of the complexes are as follows. The N-H stretching frequency occurs at around 3150 cm⁻¹ which was present at around 3350 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of free anilic acids. The carbonyl stretching frequency of the secondary amide fall within the range 1660-1680 cm⁻¹ which is well removed from 1700 cm⁻¹ band in free secondary amide. Although C=O does not take part in coordination, the shift towards lower side may be due to the mass effect of heavy metal ion linked to nitrogen¹² and thus weakening of C=O linkage¹³. The stretching bands at around 1470 cm⁻¹ (C-N) in the spectra of anilic acids shifted to about 1480 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of their complexes. The bands obtained in the region 1600-1620 and 1365-1400

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	Molar conductances $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	C	H	N		
1.	[Cr(P) ₃]	6.80 (6.74)	65.90 (65.34)	3.90 (3.92)	5.40 (5.44)	3.74	7.25
2.	[Cr(4-methyl P) ₃]	6.35 (6.39)	66.00 (66.39)	4.45 (4.46)	5.20 (5.16)	3.78	5.00
3.	[Cr(4-nitro P) ₃]	5.70 (5.73)	55.10 (55.61)	2.98 (3.00)	9.30 (9.27)	3.72	8.50
4.	[Cr(4-chloro P) ₃]	5.90 (5.94)	58.20 (57.62)	3.08 (3.11)	4.75 (4.80)	3.75	4.80
5.	[Cr(1-naphthyl P) ₃]	5.55 (5.51)	68.10 (68.77)	3.88 (3.85)	4.50 (4.46)	3.79	9.25
6.	[Cr(M) ₃]	8.40 (8.36)	58.50 (57.93)	3.92 (3.89)	6.80 (6.76)	3.75	8.00
7.	[Cr(4-methyl M) ₃]	7.80 (7.83)	59.15 (59.69)	4.52 (4.55)	6.30 (6.33)	3.73	4.20
8.	[Cr(4-nitro M) ₃]	6.90 (6.87)	43.20 (47.60)	2.82 (2.80)	11.15 (11.10)	3.72	3.60
9.	[Cr(4-chloro M) ₃]	7.20 (7.17)	49.00 (49.66)	2.90 (2.91)	5.75 (5.79)	3.74	6.30
10.	[Cr(1-naphthyl M) ₃]	6.60 (6.56)	63.05 (63.61)	3.83 (3.81)	5.27 (5.30)	3.76	6.50

*P = Phthalanilic acid, M = maleanilic acid (both contain deprotonated carboxylic acid group).

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGY (cm^{-1})

Compd. no.*	Expt. of calculation	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (ν_1)	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2)	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$	B	β_{ss}	$ \delta\nu $ cm^{-1}	$ \delta\nu $ %	LFSE k cal mol^{-1}
1	Expt. (c)	16 200	22 500	36 300	—	—	—	—	231.85
		10 Dq	22 916	35 884	680	0.74	± 416	1.49	236.75
2	Expt. (c)	16 500	22 800	36 500	—	—	—	—	236.75
		10 Dq	23 047	36 247	653	0.71	± 247 -253	0.88	241.05
3	Expt. (c)	16 800	23 000	37 000	—	—	—	—	241.05
		10 Dq	23 276	36 724	640	0.70	± 276	0.97	239.60
4	Expt. (c)	16 700	22 900	36 800	—	—	—	—	239.60
		10 Dq	23 167	36 533	640	0.70	± 267	0.94	246.77
5	Expt. (c)	17 200	23 500	37 600	—	—	—	—	246.77
		10 Dq	23 655	37 440	633	0.69	-160 $+155$	0.54	229.57
6	Expt. (c)	16 000	22 200	36 100	—	—	—	—	229.57
		10 Dq	22 743	35 562	687	0.75	-538 $+543$	1.95	233.84
7	Expt. (c)	16 300	22 500	36 300	—	—	—	—	233.84
		10 Dq	22 880	35 920	600	0.72	± 380	1.36	238.17
8	Expt. (c)	16 600	22 800	36 800	—	—	—	—	238.17
		10 Dq	23 157	36 438	653	0.71	-362 $+357$	1.26	235.29
9	Expt. (c)	16 400	22 600	36 500	—	—	—	—	235.29
		10 Dq	22 990	36 110	660	0.72	$+390$	0.89	243.89
10	Expt. (c)	17 000	23 000	37 500	—	—	—	—	243.89
		10 Dq	23 438	37 057	633	0.69	-443 $+438$	1.52	

* Corresponding to Sl. no. in Table 1.

cm^{-1} indicated the coordination through carboxylate¹⁴. The bands due to M—N and M—O were obtained at ≈ 410 and $\approx 350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

Electronic spectral studies : The values of molar conductances (Table 1) in the range 4.8-9.25 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The values of magnetic moments are close enough to spin-only value for octahedral complexes. The deviations $|\delta\nu_{2,3}|$ between the calculated and experimental values (Table 2) also

indicated an octahedral geometry for these complexes. Table 2 also contains experimental absorption band energies, the values of 10 Dq, B, β_{ss} and ligand field stabilisation energies.

The value of first spin-allowed band was directly taken as 10 Dq. The values of ν_2 and ν_3 were calculated using the standard equations which include configuration interactions¹⁵. The value of Racah's inter-electronic repulsion parameter B has been calculated by three different methods as

discussed by Konig¹⁵. It is interesting to note that the calculated values of B and nephelauxetic ratio ($\beta_{as} = B \text{ in complex} / B \text{ in free ion}$) depend significantly on the method adopted for their calculation. The calculated transition energy according to procedures (a), (b) and (c) is of the order of a few percent and decreases according to $|\delta\nu(b)| > |\delta\nu(a)| > |\delta\nu(c)|$. Thus, the values obtained by the method (c) only which provided the best fit for the transitions ν_2 and ν_3 are given in Table 2.

The reflectance spectra of the complexes also gave nearly the same bands as were obtained in their electronic spectra in solution indicating thereby no dissociation of the complexes in solution.

References

1. S. K. DATTA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 148, 267.
2. S. K. DATTA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 148, 259.
3. S. K. DATTA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 148, 334.
4. K. N. VONKAULLA, *Bibliotheca Haematol.*, 1962, 19, 174.
5. S. MALCOLM and D. PRESSMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2863.
6. S. H. UNGER and C. HANSCH, *Proc. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1976, 12, 111.
7. UPJOHN, *Brit.*, 1956, 27, 751.
8. S. HASTING and T. HENRY, 1949, 45, 2490.
9. M. P. CAVA, A. A. DEANA, K. MUTH and M. J. MITCHELL, *Org. Synth.*, 1973, 5, 944.
10. M. V. SUBBA RAO and C. V. RATNAM, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 47, 218.
11. C. L. SHARMA and T. K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 119.
12. G. NARAIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 2403.
13. G. NARAIN, P. SHUKLA and L. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 123.
14. C. L. SHARMA, T. K. DE and P. K. JAIN, *Chem. Scr.*, 1981, 18, 79.
15. E. KONIG, *Struct. Bonding*, 1971, 9, 175.